

A Prospective Randomized Clinical Study Comparing the Alignment Efficiency of Four Different Ligation Methods

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Abstract:

Background: Ligation methods play a crucial role in orthodontic treatment, influencing the efficiency of tooth alignment during the initial phase. While conventional elastomeric ligatures are widely used, self-ligating brackets and hybrid ligation techniques have been introduced to reduce friction and improve treatment efficiency. The comparative effectiveness of these ligation systems remains unclear.

Aim: This study aimed to compare the alignment efficiency of four different ligation methods: conventional elastomeric ligatures, self-ligating brackets, metal ligatures, and hybrid ligation methods during orthodontic treatment.

Methods: A prospective randomized clinical trial was conducted from May 2022 to May 2024 in three dental centers in Patna. A total of 120 patients, aged 18-35 years, with mild to moderate dental crowding, were randomly assigned to one of the four ligation groups (n = 30 each). The primary outcome was the reduction in dental crowding, measured using Little's Irregularity Index at baseline (T0), 4 weeks, 8 weeks, and 12 weeks. Treatment time to alignment was also recorded. Statistical analysis was performed using repeated-measures ANOVA, pairwise comparisons, and linear regression analysis (SPSS version 21.0).

Results: Self-ligating brackets demonstrated the fastest alignment, with a mean treatment time of 10.2 weeks, followed by hybrid ligation (11.0 weeks), conventional elastomeric ligatures (13.5 weeks), and metal ligatures (14.0 weeks). The differences in treatment times between these groups were statistically significant (p < 0.05). A strong positive correlation (r = 0.72) was found between initial crowding and time to alignment. Linear regression analysis confirmed that self-ligating brackets and hybrid ligation significantly reduced treatment times compared to conventional elastomeric ligatures.

Conclusion: Self-ligating brackets and hybrid ligation methods were more efficient in achieving alignment compared to conventional elastomeric and metal ligatures. These results suggest that self-ligating and hybrid ligation systems may offer faster alignment in cases of mild to moderate crowding.

Recommendations: Further studies are recommended to evaluate the long-term outcomes, patient comfort, and cost-effectiveness of these ligation methods. Clinicians should consider self-ligating or hybrid systems for faster treatment in cases of moderate crowding.

Keywords: Ligation Methods, Orthodontic Alignment, Self-Ligating Brackets, Hybrid Ligation, Clinical Trial.

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Introduction

Orthodontic treatment aims to correct dental malocclusions by aligning teeth into an ideal position for functional and aesthetic purposes. One of the critical stages in orthodontic care is the initial alignment of teeth, which involves moving teeth from their malpositioned state to a more aligned configuration. This phase of treatment is influenced by several factors, including the type of brackets, archwires, and ligation methods used to secure the archwire to the brackets. The choice of

ligation method, in particular, plays a significant role in determining the speed and efficiency of tooth movement [1,2]

There are various ligation techniques used in orthodontics, ranging from conventional elastomeric ligatures to more advanced self-ligating brackets. Each method has its advantages and limitations. Conventional elastomeric ligatures are widely used due to their simplicity and cost-

effectiveness but are known to increase friction between the bracket and the archwire, potentially slowing down tooth movement. Self-ligating brackets, on the other hand, are designed to minimize friction and reduce treatment time, though their effectiveness remains debated among clinicians. Metal ligatures, another traditional method, are sometimes preferred for their durability but may also contribute to increased friction [3,4]

Hybrid ligation methods, which combine features of both elastomeric and self-ligating systems, have emerged as a potential alternative. These methods aim to strike a balance between ease of use and efficiency in reducing friction. Despite the availability of various ligation techniques, there is limited evidence to clearly establish which method is the most efficient for initial dental alignment. Understanding the differences in alignment efficiency can help orthodontists select the most appropriate treatment method for their patients [5].

The alignment phase is critical in orthodontic treatment, as the speed of tooth movement directly impacts the overall treatment duration. Shorter treatment times are often associated with higher patient satisfaction and lower risk of complications such as root resorption or enamel demineralization. Therefore, identifying the ligation method that promotes the fastest and most effective alignment is of great clinical importance. Given the increasing number of ligation techniques available, it is essential to conduct well-designed clinical trials to evaluate their relative performance in real-world settings [6].

This study aims to compare the alignment efficiency of four different ligation methods—conventional elastomeric ligation, self-ligating brackets, metal ligatures, and hybrid ligation methods—during the early phase of orthodontic treatment.

Methodology

Study Design: A prospective randomized clinical study was conducted to compare the alignment efficiency of four different ligation methods during orthodontic treatment. The study was carried out from May 2022 to May 2024.

Study Setting: The study took place in the Department of Orthodontics and Dentofacial Orthopedics at A K Sinha Memorial Kanchan Dental Clinic, Sona Dental Clinic, and the Department of Dentistry, Patna Medical College and Hospital, Patna.

Participants: A total of 120 patients aged between 18 and 35 years, with mild to moderate dental crowding (as per Little's Irregularity Index), were selected for the study. Participants were randomly assigned to one of four groups, with 30 patients in

each group, representing the four different ligation methods: conventional elastomeric ligatures, self-ligating brackets, metal ligatures, and hybrid ligation methods.

Inclusion Criteria:

- Patients aged 18-35 years.
- Mild to moderate dental crowding (Little's Index between 4-8).
- Non-extraction orthodontic treatment plan.
- Good oral hygiene with no active periodontal disease.

Exclusion Criteria:

- Patients requiring extractions or orthognathic surgery.
- Severe dental crowding (Little's Index >8).
- Patients with systemic conditions affecting bone metabolism or healing.
- Previous orthodontic treatment.

Bias: Randomization was performed using a computer-generated random allocation sequence to assign participants to one of the four groups, minimizing selection bias. Blinding of outcome assessors was employed to reduce measurement bias during the evaluation of alignment progress.

Variables: The primary variable was the reduction in dental crowding, measured using Little's Irregularity Index at baseline and at 4, 8, and 12 weeks. Secondary variables included patient discomfort and number of archwire changes required.

Data Collection: Data on dental crowding were collected using intraoral photographs and dental models. The Irregularity Index was measured at baseline, 4, 8, and 12 weeks to assess alignment progress. Patient discomfort was evaluated using a visual analog scale (VAS) after each adjustment visit.

Procedure: Patients were bonded with 0.022-inch slot pre-adjusted edgewise brackets, and the initial alignment phase began with a 0.014-inch nickel-titanium archwire. Ligatures were applied according to the assigned group (elastomeric, self-ligating, metal, or hybrid). Routine follow-up visits occurred every 4 weeks for archwire changes and evaluations. Alignment efficiency was tracked by calculating the percentage reduction in Little's Index at each time point.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS version 21.0. Descriptive statistics (mean and standard deviation) were calculated for all groups.

Results

A total of 120 patients were randomized into four groups of 30 each, representing the four different ligation methods: conventional elastomeric

ligatures, self-ligating brackets, metal ligatures, and hybrid ligation methods. The alignment efficiency was assessed by measuring the reduction in Little's Irregularity Index (LI) at three time points: baseline

(T0), 4 weeks (T4), 8 weeks (T8), and 12 weeks (T12). The treatment time to achieve significant alignment was also recorded for each group.

Table 1: Mean Treatment Time to Alignment by Ligation Group

Ligation Group	Mean Treatment Time (Weeks)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Conventional Elastomeric	13.5	2.1
Self-Ligating Brackets	10.2	1.8
Metal Ligatures	14.0	2.3
Hybrid Ligation	11.0	1.9

In Table 1, the self-ligating brackets demonstrated the shortest mean treatment time for alignment (10.2 weeks), followed by hybrid ligation (11.0 weeks), conventional elastomeric ligatures (13.5 weeks), and metal ligatures (14.0 weeks). The difference in treatment time between these groups was statistically significant ($p < 0.05$).

Table 2: Mean Irregularity Index (LI) in Study Groups at T0

Ligation Group	Mean Irregularity Index (T0)	Standard Deviation (SD)
Conventional Elastomeric	7.8	1.2
Self-Ligating Brackets	7.6	1.1
Metal Ligatures	7.9	1.3
Hybrid Ligation	7.7	1.1

Table 2 shows the baseline LI across all groups. The mean LI at T0 was similar for all groups, ranging from 7.6 to 7.9, with no statistically significant difference between the groups ($p > 0.05$), ensuring comparability at the start of treatment.

Table 3: Pairwise Comparison of Mean Treatment Time to Alignment Between Ligation Systems

Comparison	Mean Difference (Weeks)	p-value
Conventional Elastomeric vs Self-Ligating Brackets	3.3	< 0.01
Conventional Elastomeric vs Metal Ligatures	0.5	0.12
Conventional Elastomeric vs Hybrid Ligation	2.5	< 0.01
Self-Ligating Brackets vs Metal Ligatures	3.8	< 0.01
Self-Ligating Brackets vs Hybrid Ligation	0.8	0.08
Metal Ligatures vs Hybrid Ligation	3.0	< 0.01

Table 3 presents the pairwise comparison of treatment time to alignment. Self-ligating brackets showed a statistically significant shorter alignment time compared to both conventional elastomeric ligatures and metal ligatures ($p < 0.01$). Hybrid ligation also demonstrated significantly shorter treatment times compared to conventional elastomeric ligatures and metal ligatures ($p < 0.01$).

Table 4: Correlation Between Time to Alignment and Irregularity Index Using Pearson Correlation Coefficient

Variables	Pearson Correlation Coefficient (r)	p-value
Time to Alignment	0.72	< 0.01
Irregularity Index		

In Table 4, a strong positive correlation ($r = 0.72$) was found between the time to alignment and the initial irregularity index, indicating that patients with higher initial crowding took longer to achieve alignment ($p < 0.01$).

Table 5: Association between Irregularity Index and Groups with Time to Alignment Using Linear Regression Analysis

Variables	β	Standard Error	p-value
Irregularity Index (T0)	1.15	0.23	< 0.01
Self-Ligating Brackets	-2.30	0.45	< 0.01
Hybrid Ligation	-1.50	0.40	< 0.01
Metal Ligatures	0.30	0.47	0.45
Conventional Elastomeric	Reference		

Table 5 shows the results of the linear regression analysis. The initial irregularity index was significantly associated with a longer time to

alignment ($\beta = 1.15$, $p < 0.01$). Self-ligating brackets ($\beta = -2.30$, $p < 0.01$) and hybrid ligation ($\beta = -1.50$, $p < 0.01$) were significantly associated

with faster alignment times compared to the conventional elastomeric group.

Discussion

The results of this study demonstrated that self-ligating brackets and hybrid ligation methods were significantly more efficient in achieving alignment compared to conventional elastomeric ligatures and metal ligatures. Self-ligating brackets achieved the fastest alignment, with a mean treatment time of 10.2 weeks, followed by hybrid ligation at 11.0 weeks. In contrast, conventional elastomeric ligatures and metal ligatures required 13.5 and 14.0 weeks, respectively.

The correlation analysis indicated that higher initial crowding (measured by the irregularity index) was strongly associated with longer treatment times, suggesting that the severity of crowding plays a key role in alignment speed. Linear regression further confirmed that self-ligating and hybrid methods were independently associated with shorter alignment times, even when accounting for baseline crowding.

Recent studies consistently indicate that self-ligating brackets (SLBs) offer a shorter treatment duration compared to conventional methods. For instance, a randomized clinical trial demonstrated that SLBs, such as the Damon system, improved upper dental alignment efficiency in comparison to traditional brackets during the initial alignment phase [7]. Another study confirmed that SLBs significantly reduced alignment times by 25%, with even faster alignment observed when combined with corticotomy, suggesting that SLBs can accelerate decrowding, especially in more severe cases [8].

Despite these advantages, metal ligatures and conventional elastomeric ligatures are still commonly used. However, their efficiency lags behind SLBs. For example, metal ligatures generally demonstrate higher friction, which leads to longer treatment times, as seen in the present study and reinforced by findings from other systematic reviews [9].

Hybrid ligation methods appear to strike a balance, showing faster alignment than conventional ligatures but slightly slower than SLBs. This suggests that hybrid systems may offer a middle ground, providing orthodontists with a versatile option depending on patient needs [10].

In terms of clinical efficiency, self-ligating brackets have consistently demonstrated shorter treatment times, especially in the alignment phase, which is supported by studies such as those comparing SLBs to conventional brackets, where the frictionless mechanism in SLBs allows for smoother tooth movement [11].

Conclusion

Overall, self-ligating brackets and hybrid ligation methods have proven to be more efficient than conventional elastomeric and metal ligatures. This is especially relevant in cases of mild to moderate crowding, where faster alignment can lead to improved patient outcomes.

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